

CORDEX Archive Design

The following recommendations apply both to CORDEX runs driven by ERA-Interim and CMIP5-GCMs, in terms of : variables to be saved, output format and frequency, file naming and archiving.

(a) Three classes of data are defined:

Core, relevant to all communities: monthly and seasonal means;

Tier 1, relevant to most communities: daily surface/selected upper air data;

Tier 2, higher frequency and more complete atmospheric/surface variables.

(b) Core data should be easily accessible as data-files (on standard lat-long grids).

(c) Core and tier 1 variables will be held in a central archive in easily downloadable, quality controlled netcdf files conforming to agreed standards.

(d) Tier 2 variables will be stored locally at modelling centres and made available on a more informal basis, e.g. bilaterally or with projects.

(e) Experience from existing archives should inform the development of the CORDEX archive with the Danish Meteorological Institute (which holds the ENSEMBLES RCM archive) taking the role as initial host for the first set of experiments. More details on the location and transfer procedure to DMI will occur soon.

Technical specification of archive content

1. Horizontal grids

- native grid for primary output (Tier 1, Tier 2, group 1 and group 2 below)
- native **and** lat/lon grids for time averages (Core variables below).
- *N.B. A set of agreed lat/lon grids plus a template interpolation procedure will be supplied in the early fall 2009.*

2. 3D data

- These will be saved at the home institution, to be provided to people who request 3D fields

3. Time coordinate: days from a specified reference point

Proposed: 1 December 1949, 00 UTC. This would be the earliest starting time among the simulations whilst allowing for seasonal and annual averaging on standard seasonal boundaries.

4. Day boundary

- 00 UTC for all fields

5. NetCDF with CF conventions

- follow PCMDI and CMIP5 as much as possible, including metadata with the starting point being the NARCCAP output formatting requirements (including metadata) http://rcmlab.agron.iastate.edu/narccap/output_requirements.html

6. Time periods for each data file.

For 3 hourly, 6 hourly data and daily data : 1 file per 5-year period for each respective output frequency.

For monthly and seasonal data, 10 years with 1 file for each averaging period.

7. File naming conventions

Proposed: File names should follow this structure:

VariableName_ModelName_Domain_Frequency_StartTime_EndTime.nc

Where:

"VariableName" is the IPCC/CF-convention Variable Name.

"ModelName" is a 4-character identifier chosen by the modeling group (please clear it with the archival group beforehand to avoid conflicts, contacts for archival group : Richard Jones MOHC : richard.jones@metoffice.com or Bill Gutowski (ISU) gutowski@iastate.edu)

"Domain" is a standard name (To Be Decided) assigned to each of the CORDEX domains

"Frequency" is the output frequency indicator: 03H=3 hourly, 06H=6 hourly, DAM=Daily, MOM=Monthly, SEM=Seasonal

"StartTime" is the starting time of the file, in the form "YearMonthDayUTC", e.g., 1979010100 for 00 UTC on 1 Jan 1979.

"EndTime" is the ending time of the file, in the form "YearMonthDayUTC", e.g., 1984123121 for 21 UTC on 31 Dec 1984.

8. Suggested variables to output

N.B. Upward directed fluxes (from surface towards atmosphere defined as negative). Downward directed fluxes (from atmosphere to surface defined as positive)

Core: Monthly and seasonal output.

1. 2-metre air temperature (K)
2. Maximum 2-metre air temperature (monthly average of daily max)
3. Minimum 2-metre air temperature (monthly average of daily min)
4. Precipitation (kg/m²/s)
5. Mean sea level pressure (hpa)
6. 2-metre specific humidity (kg/kg)
7. 10m wind speed (m/s)
8. Maximum 10-metre wind speed (monthly average of daily max)
9. Total Cloud Cover (%)
10. Sunshine Hours (s) (Presently defined as seconds when surface solar radiation flux exceeds 120 W/m²)

11. Surface Downwelling Shortwave Radiation (W/m²)
12. Surface Downwelling Longwave Radiation (W/m²)
13. Surface Latent Heat Flux (W/m²)
14. Surface Sensible Heat Flux (W/m²)
15. Upwelling Surface Shortwave Radiation (W/m²)
16. Upwelling Longwave radiation (W/m²)

17. Surface Evaporation (kg/m²/s)
18. Soil Frozen Water Content (*m*)
19. Surface Runoff (kg/m²/s)
20. Subsurface Runoff (kg/m²/s)
21. Total Soil Moisture Content (*m*)
22. Snow Depth (m)
23. Snow Melt (kg/m²/s)

24. TOA Outgoing Longwave Radiation (Wm²)

25. TOA Incident Shortwave Radiation (Wm²)
26. TOA Outgoing Shortwave Radiation (Wm²)

27. E-W directed 10m wind velocity (m/s)
28. N-S directed 10m wind velocity (m/s)

29. Zonal (east-west) wind at 850 hPa
30. Meridional (north-south) wind at 850 hPa
31. Temperature at 850 hPa
32. Specific humidity at 850 hPa
33. Zonal (east-west) wind at 500 hPa
34. Meridional (north-south) wind at 500 hPa
35. Geopotential height at 500 hPa (in metres)
36. Temperature at 500 hPa
37. Zonal (east-west) wind at 200 hPa
38. Meridional (north-south) wind at 200 hPa
39. Temperature at 200 hPa
40. Geopotential at 200 hPa

Variables 1-3, 5-9, 18, 21, 22, 27-40 instantaneous and then meaned into the monthly/seasonal time period)

Other variables accumulated and then averaged into monthly/seasonal.

Tier 1: Daily average output.

1. 2-metre air temperature (K)
2. Maximum 2-metre air temperature (for the 24 hour period preceding the write point)
3. Minimum 2-metre air temperature (for the 24 hour period preceding the write point)
4. Precipitation (kg/m²/s)
5. Surface Pressure (hPa)
6. Mean sea level pressure (hPa)
7. 2-metre Specific Humidity (kg/kg)
8. 10m wind speed (m/s)
9. Maximum 10-metre wind speed (for the 24 hour period preceding the write point)
10. Total Cloud Cover (%)
11. Sunshine Hours (s)
12. Surface Downwelling Shortwave Radiation (W/m²)
13. Surface Downwelling Longwave Radiation (W/m²)
14. Surface Latent Heat Flux (W/m²)
15. Surface Sensible Heat Flux (W/m²)
16. Surface Upwelling Shortwave Radiation (W/m²)
17. Surface Upwelling Longwave radiation (W/m²)

18. Surface Evaporation (kg/m²/s)
19. Potential evapotranspiration if available (kg/m²/s)

20. Soil Frozen Water Content (*m*)
 21. Surface Runoff (kg/m²/s)
 22. Subsurface Runoff (kg/m²/s)
 23. Total Soil Moisture Content (*m*)
 24. Snow Depth (m)
 25. Snow Melt (kg/m²/s)
 26. Maximum 1-hour precipitation rate within the 24 hour period (kg/m²/s)
 27. Convective Precipitation (kg/m²/s)
 28. TOA Outgoing Longwave Radiation (Wm²)
 29. TOA Incident Shortwave Radiation (Wm²)
 30. TOA Outgoing Shortwave Radiation (Wm²)
 31. E-W 10m wind speed (m/s)
 32. N-S 10m wind speed (m/s)
 33. Maximum 10-metre GUST wind speed if available
 34. Surface Downward Flux of Eastward Momentum (kgm/s/m²)
 35. Surface Downward Flux of Northward Momentum (kgm/s/m²)
 36. Surface (skin) Temperature (K)
 37. Atmospheric Boundary Layer Thickness (m)
 38. Column water vapour (m)
 39. Column liquid water content (m)
 40. Column Ice water content (m)

 41. Zonal (east-west) wind at 850 hPa
 42. Meridional (north-south) wind at 850 hPa
 43. Temperature at 850 hPa
 44. Specific humidity at 850 hPa

 45. Zonal (east-west) wind at 500 hPa
 46. Meridional (north-south) wind at 500 hPa
 47. Geopotential height at 500 hPa
 48. Temperature at 500 hPa

 49. Zonal (east-west) wind at 200 hPa
 50. Meridional (north-south) wind at 200 hPa
 51. Temperature at 200 hpa
 52. Geopotential at 200hpa

 53. High Clouds (p<440hpa) if available
 54. Medium Clouds (660 < p < 440) if available
 55. Low Clouds (p>660hpa) if available
- For each cloud layer use the same overlap assumption as used in the radiation scheme, but performed from an assumption of zero cloud above from each layer nearest to the upper pressure level definition (High=top model level, Medium=440hpa, Low=660hpa).*

Variables 1-3, 5-10,20,23,24,31-33,36-55 saved as instantaneous values and then meaned over the relevant time period)

Other variables accumulated and then averaged.

Tier 2: Sub-daily output

Group 1 : 3-hourly fields.

Fields 1-17 of the tier 1 variables excepting 2,3 and 9.

State variables should be instantaneous, fluxes as accumulations.
Instantaneous = 1,5,6,7,8 and accumulations=4,10,11-17

Group 2 : 6-hourly fields.

Fields 18-55 of the tier 1 variables excepting 26 and 33.

Instantaneous = 20,23,24,31,32,36-55
Accumulations = 18,19,21,22,27-30,34,35